

Interaction between Forestry and Livestock

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Sheep and goats shape the forest area, keeping forest biomass low, reducing the risk of forest fires. Stenoma, Municipality of Karpenisi (photo by V.Lappa)

The observed reduction of extensive grazing in the geographical region of Evrytania has allowed the expansion of forests and the subsequent replacement of the former open silvopastoral areas with dense shrubs and grassland. This, combined with the extension of the dry season during the summer months, increased the risk of forest fires. Under these circumstances, sustainable rural development, with livestock and beekeeping as agroforestry production activities, which represents one of the strategic goals to support local population by providing financial incentives in mountainous areas, is in doubt.

Regular grazing to control natural vegetation in strategic areas linked to fire prevention (forest-habitat interface areas, fire safety zones, etc.) is a sustainable agroforestry practice in which livestock (small ruminants) are used as a "tool" to minimise forest fire risk by controlling vegetation growth. Thus, in addition to the productive service provided by grazing, another ecological function is also achieved for woodland and forests that either surround open pastures or are themselves pasture, such as the wooded grasslands that contain native forest species (deciduous and non-deciduous oaks, junipers etc), and wild fruit trees (wild pear, wild apples, hawthorns, blackthorn etc). These areas maintain a high biodiversity of wild fauna and flora and are areas of high ecological value.

In addition, livestock farming is a key element for the reassessment and multifunctional management of forests with very little timber exploitation. In this sense, it also contributes to the recognition of the contribution of the shepherd and his presence in the forests as a guardian and volunteer for fire safety.

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